

Analysis of the Quality of Port Authority Services to Shipping Companies at Tanjung Perak Port Surabaya

Prawiraharja¹

Rahmat Agus Santoso²

¹University of Muhammadiyah Gresik Magister Manajemen
Pascasarjana Gresik City East Java Indonesia

²University of Muhammadiyah Gresik Magister Manajemen
Pascasarjana Gresik City East Java Indonesia

Eva Desembrianita³

³University of Muhammadiyah Gresik Magister Manajemen Pascasarjana
Gresik City East Java Indonesia

Abstract:- The purpose of this study was to determine how the Port Authority Service Quality Analysis of Shipping Companies at Tanjung Perak Port Surabaya. The methodology used in this research is a qualitative research method which is a method used to examine natural objects where the researcher is the key instrument, data collection techniques are carried out by triangulation, analysis is inductive, and emphasizes meaning rather than generalization. The results of this study indicate that PT Dharma Lautan Utama is a roro ship shipping company that has long been operating in the Tanjung Perak Port area and has a commitment to timely ship departures. The quality of service that has the most influence on ship operations is accurate service (Realibility) and Assurance which provides certainty and assurance that the ship can dock according to the schedule set by the Port Authority so that ship operations can run smoothly.

Keywords:- Service Quality, Port Authority, Shipping Company, Transportation Port.

I. INTRODUCTION

➤ Introduce the Problem

A port is a place consisting of land and surrounding waters, with certain limits as a place for government activities and economic activities used as a place for ships to lean on, anchor, board passengers and/or load and unload

goods equipped with shipping safety facilities and activities. port support as well as a place for intra and inter-modal transfers of transportation (UU. No. 17 of 2008).

According to Triatmodjo (2003) Port is an area of water that is protected against waves, which is equipped with sea terminal facilities including a pier where ships can moor for loading and unloading, equipped with loading and unloading equipment facilities and storage areas where goods can be stored for a certain period of time. certain.

Tanjung Perak Port in Surabaya as one of the largest ports in Indonesia has strategic value and has potential as a port for collecting natural resources originating from the hinterland which is quite large and continues to grow. Therefore the role of Tanjung Perak Port in Surabaya is quite important for international trade activities (export-import), encouraging domestic trade as well as regional development and economic growth efforts in East Java Province in particular, as well as eastern Indonesia in general.

The growth of the industrial sector in East Java and Eastern Indonesia has caused the number of ship visits to the Port of Tanjung Perak to increase, so that loading and unloading activities at the Port of Tanjung Perak have also increased. Tanjung Perak Port is one of the ports managed by PT Pelindo III (Persero) which has its head office in Surabaya, manages 43 of the largest ports in 7 Provinces,

and has 7 subsidiary companies and according to Law No. 17 of 2008 concerning Operation of Public Ports, PT Pelindo III (Persero) is responsible for Shipping Safety, Port Management, Water Transportation and the Maritime Environment.

To increase productivity in the activities of shipping companies, quality service is needed for customers and the most important thing is the accuracy of the ship's departure schedule. In terms of determining ship departure schedules, it is very dependent on port facilities managed by PT Pelindo III (Persero), namely the dock for ship berths in loading and unloading activities as well as the regulator that carries out supervision, namely the Port Authority (OP).

According to the regulation of the Minister of Transportation Number PM 35 of 2012 concerning the Organization and Work Procedure of the Port Authority. The Main Shipping Port Authority Office is a Technical Implementation Unit within the Ministry of Transportation which is under and responsible to the Director General of Sea Transportation. The Main Port Authority Office has the task of carrying out the regulation, control and supervision of port activities at commercially operated ports. Seeing the current conditions, the facilities and infrastructure of the Tanjung Perak Main Port Authority Office can still be said to be limited, but under certain conditions it is demanded that they be able to do optimally in carrying out their duties and functions.

The Port of Tanjung Perak has been stagnant since 2012. Only the Jamrud Utara pier and the Kade Perak Pier are still below the Berth Occupancy Ratio (BOR) standard set at 70%. There is also over-capacity at the Port of Tanjung Perak (Adhiyakso, et al, 2012). With the condition of fixed facilities and infrastructure and often not accompanied by optimization of port performance, of course this has the potential to cause queues of ships to dock at the Port of Tanjung Perak resulting in greater waiting times for ships as a result of which the performance of the Port is less than optimal which will incur high economic costs, which will have a direct impact on the price of goods in the market. As many people know, the largest logistics costs in Indonesia are at ports and this is a national problem.

To optimize port facilities in loading and unloading activities, an integrated system is needed that can be accessed by all parties, especially in the process of determining the place and time for ships to dock at the wharf. In this case the Port Authority provides an opportunity for all ship operators to provide plans for ship activities and to determine moorings at the PPSA office (One Roof Service Center). Decisions in determining moorings may result in discrepancies with ship operator activity plans due to limited berths. Priority is given to berthing activities for the arrival of ships that arrive earlier to carry out unloading activities and if possible can be directly loaded according to the time specified. The moorings that have been set are not a guarantee that the ship can dock on time and still depends on operating conditions rational on the wharf.

The role of the Port Authority is very important in supervising the decision to determine moorings which is the core of a series of port service activities. The smooth process of docking the ship will have an impact on the speed of loading and unloading which can increase customer confidence to use safe and comfortable modes of sea transportation. There are problems at the moorings apart from the limited berths which are no longer in accordance with the number and size of ships docked, also influenced by the non-compliance of the ship operators themselves in carrying out the mooring determination results, namely trying to maximize cargo with the intention of increasing productivity and ignoring decisions made especially when the operator ships have the same schedule as competitors. Supervision carried out so far can be said to be still weak and has not provided A deterrent effect so that similar incidents still occur repeatedly.

The Port Authority cannot provide other alternative berths if the mooring is still being used by other ship operators and before being able to carry out unloading activities the ship carries out the berthing process which poses a risk to the safety of the ship and incurs additional costs other than berthing costs, namely berthing fees. Berthing activities cause a lot of losses for ship operators, especially in the satisfaction of service users who entrust the delivery of logistics goods.

For this reason, it is necessary to improve the quality of service from the Port Authority to be able to overcome this problem with several factors that can be done to be able to reduce and anticipate if there is a queue of ships which can cause waiting time for ships at the port.

The mooring schedule that has been determined for ship berthing activities is often not in accordance with the initial determination so that it affects the ship's departure schedule that has been determined. It is hoped that the results of this research can become input in achieving efficiency and effectiveness of services for ships and goods at ports and support efforts to improve port performance and productivity

- *Why is this problem important?*
- *How does the study relate to previous work in the area? If other aspects of this study have been reported previously,*
- *how does this report differ from, and build on, the earlier report?*
- *What are the primary and secondary hypotheses and objectives of the study, and what, if any, are the links to theory?*
- *How do the hypotheses and research design relate to one another?*
- *What are the theoretical and practical implications of the study?*

A good introduction answers these questions in just a few pages and, by summarizing the relevant arguments and the past evidence, gives the reader a firm sense of What was done and why (Beck & Sales, 2001, pp. 100-102).

➤ *Explore Importance of the Problem*

How is the Analysis of Service Quality of the Port Authority for Shipping Companies at the Port of Tanjung Perak, Surabaya .

➤ *Describe Relevant Scholarship*

To find out how to analyze the service quality of the port authority for shipping companies at the Port of Tanjung Perak, Surabaya.

➤ *State Hypotheses and their Correspondence to Research Design*

Based on the relationship between the main dimensions of service variables, namely tangible, responsiveness, reliability, assurance, empathy, the researcher created a model that was used as the basis for this research.

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How is the Analysis of Port Authority Service Quality for Shipping Companies at the Port of Tanjung Perak Surabaya? To find out how to analyze the service quality of the port authority for shipping companies at the Port of Tanjung Perak, Surabaya.

II. METHOD

Research on the government agency Port Authority (Port Authority) as the authorized party in allocating moorings on ships owned by shipping companies from PT. Dharma Lautan Utama was carried out qualitatively because there were phenomena that could not be described quantitatively. So this research was conducted qualitatively to be able to reveal more details about the phenomena found by researchers so that the problems can be studied in more depth. In line with the opinion of Sugiyono (2010: 8) the qualitative research method is a method used to research natural objects where the researcher is a key instrument, data collection techniques are carried out by triangulation, analysis is inductive, and emphasizes meaning rather than generalization.

➤ *Identify Subsections*

In order to obtain valid and accurate data and information, in-depth interviews were conducted with informants who were used as sources of information. Meanwhile, the selected informants are those who are directly involved and understand and can provide information (illustration) about port operations.

➤ *Participant (Subject) Characteristics*

There are 4 (four) Informants that the Author Involved in this Study, Namely: List of Research Informants

- *Donie Surya Putra, SE, MM Branch Manager Key Informant*
- *Purwanto, SE Head of Supporting Informant Operations*
- *Eka Prasetya Supporting Informant Certification Staff*
- *Bagus Supporting Informant Service Staff.*

➤ *Sampling Procedures*

Represents data in verbal form or spoken words, gestures or behavior carried out by trusted subjects, namely research subjects or informants relating to the variables studied or data obtained from respondents directly. (Arikunto, 2010; 22).

Primary data obtained through direct interviews with parties from PT. Dharma Lautan Utama as well as observations with direct observations of the company. Through interviews, questions were asked about the general description that occurred at PT. Dharma Lautan Utama which carries out the decisions of the Port Authority at the Port of Tanjung Perak.

III. RESULTS

Shipping companies, especially ro-ro ships, are an alternative for passenger and vehicle transportation both personally and for business purposes. The establishment of PT Dharma Lautan Utama in 1976 was the first step in the development of regions in the archipelago that had not been reached by land transportation, now they can be reached by sea transportation. With the operation of ro-ro ships, it can reduce the high price difference between Java Island and other islands, this is because sea transportation has the advantage of being large loading capacity and relatively cheap prices.

The existence of the Port Authority plays an important role in supporting the smooth running of shipping activities. Starting from berthing ships, loading and unloading and ships departing within the port area. The success of the ship's operational activities can be seen from the accuracy

of the departure schedule. This success is supported by adequate port facilities and the division of berths in accordance with the ship's departure schedule. Since economic growth has increased and many passengers have switched to sea transportation, many new shipping companies have started operating ships at the Port of Tanjung Perak and this is not in line with the construction of a pier for ship berthing activities. The number of piers, especially for ro-ro ships, is very limited, thus hampering the ship's operational activities which results in delays in departure schedules.

Since the formation of the Port Authority, which is a good move by the government to improve healthy competence and work efficiency at all ports in the country, it has begun to show some improvements in the administrative system, namely by starting to implement an information system that can be accessed by all shipping companies with the aim of cutting bureaucratic flows in shipping. ship operational activities, especially the management of berths at the wharf.

Analysis of service quality at the Tanjung Perak Port Authority is carried out according to the dimensions of service quality as follows:

➤ *Physical Evidence (Tangible) of the Emerald Pier*

There are 2 (two) piers that are used in the ro-ro ship docking service, namely Jamrud Utara and Jamrud Selatan, where ships owned by PT Dharma Lautan Utama use the two dock facilities by adjusting the size of the ship.

Determination of moorings that are not in accordance with the tides will cause difficulties for the ship in the process of loading and unloading vehicles, which is the reason for the delay in the ship's schedule (delay). Determination of berthing time is prioritized for ships that arrive first and in accordance with the size of the pier that will be used for ship operational activities. The results of mooring determination are informed to ro-ro ship companies which are used as a reference for ship operational activities. Determination of mooring results is carried out 1 (one) day before the ship's schedule and can be revised if things happen that are outside of operational constraints in general such as bad weather conditions so that there is a delay in

the ship's docking schedule.

➤ *Responsiveness (Responsiveness) the Officer Watch*

In realizing order at the port, reliable officers from the Port Authority, namely the Officer on Watch, are required to oversee the ship's operational activities. With the Officer on Watch the conformity in the implementation of the ship's berth can be carried out in accordance with the results of the mooring determination meeting. When a discrepancy occurs due to an indication of the intention of the ro-ro ship company to increase the berthing time in the process of increasing the amount of cargo, the Officer on Watch can immediately confirm and give a warning so that the loading activity is immediately stopped to prepare berths for other shipping companies that have the next docking schedule. Companies that violate the provisions must immediately take action so that the incident does not recur and harm other shipping companies. The following is an example of an incident from a ship owned by PT Mutiara Ferindo Internusa, namely KM Mutiara Ferindo 2, which received a mooring time for loading and unloading activities on January 22, 2022 starting at 04.00 WIB – 15.00 WIB and only leaving on January 22, 2022 at 00.00 WIB so that there was a setback the schedule for the ship behind it belongs to PT Dharma Lautan Utama, namely KM Dharma Kartika 9, the initial schedule is January 22, 2022 at 23.00 WIB to January 23 2022 at 07.00 WIB or a delay of 8 (eight) hours. This shows that the decision to determine the berth that is agreed upon by all shipping companies is not carried out with full commitment and is detrimental to other shipping companies.

➤ *Accurate Service (Reliability) Mooring Schedule*

Accurate information from ro-ro ship shipping companies in the form of estimated time of arrival, loading and unloading time requirements must be reported to the Port Authority for consideration in determining the ship's berth. The Port Authority also has data on all ships and their specifications owned by ro-ro shipping companies. So that when submitting a mooring by the shipping company it can be concluded and does not conflict with the mooring schedule of other shipping companies. The results of the meeting for the distribution of mooring schedules as a means of increasing ship productivity from shipping companies must be determined accurately according to

needs and there are always alternatives if there are simultaneous schedules by different shipping companies. So far, the alternative given is that the ship must dock to wait for the berth to be empty due to the ship's size constraints.

➤ *Assurance Officers with Integrity*

The Port Authority should have taken concrete steps to ensure the implementation of regulations at the port, especially by refusing extortion in the port area. The orderliness of the port depends on the integrity of the authorized officers to enforce the regulations that have been made. So that in the ship's operational activities there is a sense of security because the regulations have been enforced. In an effort to implement the regulations, officers from the Port Authority in the field are also under pressure, especially from shipping companies which have the aim of competing with other shipping companies. So that there is unhealthy competition and the impact on the schedule setback behind it. To provide guarantees so that non-compliance does not occur again in carrying out the results of the mooring meeting. The Port Authority through the head of the field (kabid) confirms directly to the leadership of the shipping company and asks to make a statement to be able to carry out activities in accordance with the mooring distribution that has been determined.

➤ *Empathy (Empathy) for Shipping Companies*

The Port Authority pays attention to shipping companies that follow procedures and carry out the results of the mooring determination meetings accordingly. The attention given is in the form of convenience in the event of technical problems during the ship's operational activities. The attention given is because the Port Authority believes that the shipping company will contribute to the port's performance in healthy competence. Because the plans for berths and ship operational activities are in accordance with shipping company standards, especially the timeliness of the schedule.

IV. DISCUSSION

- *Based on the results of the discussion on the research that has been carried out, some conclusions from this study are:*
- *PT Dharma Lautan Utama is a roro ship shipping company that has been operating for a long time in the Tanjung Perak Port area and has a commitment to ship departure on time.*
 - *The quality of service that has the most influence on ship operations is Reliability and Assurance which provide certainty and assurance that ships can dock according to the schedule set by the Port Authority so that ship operations can run smoothly.*
 - *Through enforcing regulations carried out by the Port Authority, it can improve port competence and contribute to shipping companies to increase their business productivity.*

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

- *Based on the conclusions which are the findings of the research results, suggestions that can be submitted are as follows:*
- *The Port Authority as a regulator must be able to provide priority scales for shipping companies that carry out the results of the decision to determine moorings consistently and provide guidance for shipping companies that violate the decisions that have been stipulated.*
 - *The Port Authority through the officer on duty is always present in the ship's operational activities and ensures that it is in accordance with the decisions made at the mooring determination meeting.*
 - *The Port Authority must have high integrity in enforcing regulations in the port area so that it can provide a sense of security for roro shipping companies in ship operations.*

REFERENCES

- [1]. Adhiyakso, T. W., & Hadi, F. (2012). Evaluasi Lokasi Pengembangan Pelabuhan Tanjung Perak. Surabaya: ITS Press Parasuraman et al., (1985). "A conceptual model of service quality and its implications for future research" Journal of marketing Vol. 49.
- [2]. Arikunto, S. 2010. Prosedur Penelitian Suatu Pendekatan Praktik. Jakarta: Rineka Maryadi, dkk. 2010. Pedoman Penulisan Skripsi FKIP. Surakarta: Universitas Muhammadiyah Surakarta.
- [3]. Asiyanto. 2008. Metode Konstruksi Jembatan Beton. UI Press, Jakarta.
- [4]. Capt. R. P. Suyono, M.Mar, 2007, Shipping Pengangkutan Intermodal Ekspor Impor Melalui Laut Edisi IV, Jakarta.
- [5]. Engkos Kosasih, Hananto soewedo (2007). Manajemen perusahaan pelayaran: suatu pendekatan praktis dalam bidang usaha pelayaran-Ed. 1-1- Jakarta: PT RajaGrafindo Persada
- [6]. Fandy, Tjiptono. 2016. Service, Quality & satisfaction. Yogyakarta. Andi.
- [7]. Hasibuan, Malayu SP, (2009), Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia, Jakarta : Bumi Aksara.
- [8]. Kolanovic, I., Skenderovic, J. & Zenzerovic Z.(2008), "Defining the Port Service Quality Model by using the Factor Analysis", Pomorstvo, 22(2):283-297 Photis M. Panayides dan Dong-Wook Song (2006).
- [9]. Kotler (2000) Kotler, Philip (2000). Prinsip-Prinsip Pemasaran Manajemen, Jakarta : Prenhalindo.
- [10]. Menteri Perhubungan (2012), Peraturan Menteri Perhubungan Nomor : PM 35 Tahun 2012 Tentang Organisasi dan Tata Kerja Otoritas Pelabuhan. Menteri Perhubungan. Jakarta.
- [11]. Panayides, Photis M. & Song, Dong-Wook, 2006. Supply Chain Orientation and Port Performance, IAME, University of Hongkong.
- [12]. Sugiyono. 2016. Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, R&D. Bandung : IKAPI.
- [13]. Thoha, Chabib (1996). Kapita Selektta Pendidikan Islam. Yogyakarta: Pusataka Belajar.
- [14]. Tongzon., J.L. (2004). Determinant of Competitiveness in Logistics: Implication for the Region. International Conference on Competitiveness: Challenges and Opportunity for Asian Countries.

- [15]. Triatmodjo, B. 2010. Perencanaan Pelabuhan. Penerbit BETA OFFSET, Edisi Pertama, Yogyakarta.
- [16]. Triatmodjo, Bambang, 2003, Pelabuhan, Beta offset, Yogyakarta.
- [17]. Undang-Undang Republik Indonesia No. 17 tahun 2008 Tentang Pelayaran.
- [18]. Zakaria, A, Firdaus, M R (2017). Jurnal Wawasan Manajemen, Vol. 5, Nomor 2, Juni 2017.